

School Preparedness for the Mandatory Implementation of Face-To-Face Classes and Its Impact to Teaching Qualities in the New Normal

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ABSTRACT: This research used descriptive correlational research design to find significant relationship between the extent of school preparedness in the mandatory implementation of five days face-to-face classes and its possible impact to teaching qualities. The respondents of this study were 188 teachers of Candelaria West District of Quezon. It was conducted during the third quarter of SY 2022-2023. Description of the profile revealed that the respondents are mostly female, aged between 46-50, mostly taking their post graduate degree, and majority of them have been in the service for five years. The perceived level of preparedness of the school in terms of facilities, school programs, safety protocols, and students and parent's awareness were always prepared. The perceived level of the teachers' practices in the new normal in terms of Classroom Management, classroom instruction and collaborative activities was always practice while professional development was in the practiced spot. All the variables are correlated to each other indicating that school preparedness has significant relationship to the teaching qualities of the teachers as perceived by the respondents. Thus, the hypothesis stating that school preparedness has no significant impact to teacher's teaching qualities in terms of classroom management, classroom instruction, professional development and collaborative activities.

KEYWORDS: Face-to-face classes, school preparedness, teacher's teaching qualities.

INTRODUCTION

The massive disruption faced by the world has brought everyone into a completely tough situation because of the novel corona virus which was the main reason that all schools both private and public are being forced to close and refrain from face-to-face classes (OECD,2020). The pandemic has compelled the world to adopt distance learning for basic education which has never done before (Briones, 2020).

After two school years of distance learning using modular instruction and/or blended learning, the Department of Education now formally opens the school year 2022-2023 with a progressive expansion of the face-to-face classes across the country. It is based on the Department of Education Memorandum Order No. 30 of the 2022 Revised School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT) to prepare schools to conduct in-person classes safely, effectively and efficiently. The Department of Education with its new Secretary and Vice President of the country, Sara Duterte emphasized the significant value of opening the school year with a full face-to-face class. She believes that to equip the children with right knowledge and skill set, teaching them with the face-to-face learning is necessary. This is one of the reasons why "OPLAN BALIK ESKWELA" is launched for 2022 classes (Malipot M. Manila Bulletin, August 21,2022).

Teachers, both in the private and public schools uphold its commitment to learning continuity amid the COVID-19 pandemic have shown an excitement of the decision made by the department. They feel that empty halls and corridors of the schools nationwide will now be filled with students and happy to meet again their classmates and school friends as well as their teachers whom they missed for more than two years. Despite the excitement, recognizing the challenges with the reintroduction of in-person learning preparations of the schools have been underway before the conduct of the full face-to-face classes. It is believed that DepEd is confident enough that the schools in the country are ready for this coming school year. The question is "how ready are the schools in this year opening of classes? Are we really ready for this face-to-face class? With the total of 1.2 million kids aged 5-11 years old and 9.7 million minors that have already been vaccinated and the resumption of schools through face to face this year, how ready are our children, teachers and schools in this new normal face-to-face class? These are the queries that the researcher would like to be enlightened, thus, this research is being conducted.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study proposed to find out the preparedness of the school and the teachers for the mandatory implementation of face-to-face classes by the department of education.

This study aims to find out the school preparedness and its impact to teacher’s teaching qualities.

The study gets the views of the teachers on how prepared are their schools in the mandatory face-to-face learning of the students in terms of facilities, school programs, safety protocols, and also teachers and parents’ awareness. In terms of teacher’s teaching qualities their perceived level of preparedness too was measured in terms of classroom management, classroom instruction, professional development and collaborative activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study is descriptive and correlative in nature. A design is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships between variables without establishing causality, or in describing variables and the relationships that occur naturally between them. The descriptive research process consists of data collection and tabulation. It is used as a research method to obtain answers from research subjects using questionnaires.

In this study, the descriptive correlational method was used to describe the relationship between perceptions of the respondents toward school preparedness and teacher’s quality.

RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The respondents of the study were teachers from Public Elementary Schools of Candelaria West District in Quezon. The eleven (11) schools included in the study are hereby presented.

Table 1

Distribution of Teacher-Respondents

School	Population Sample
A	8
B	15
C	11
D	24
E	32
F	39
G	10
H	6
I	6
J	31
K	6
TOTAL	188

Total number of the respondents was utilized to get higher number of responses for higher reliability and internal validity of the results. This was conducted during the Third quarter of the school year 2022-2023. Researcher-made survey questionnaire which was an adapted, modified and based on the DepEd Memorandum Order No.30, s. of 2022, Revised School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT) was used in the study.

Research Instrument

Researchers used the 2022 Revised School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT), U.S. Department of Education Memorandum Order No. 30, 2022, page 30, to prepare schools to safely, effectively, and efficiently conduct in-person classes. Adapted, modified and based research tools based on. The instrument contains the profile of the respondents such as name (optional), sex, age, educational attainment, and length of service that’s somehow help the respondents in determining the relationship of facilities and teachers qualities.

The second part was composed of the statements on the school preparedness and measured through LIKERT scaling of 1 to 4 comprising descriptive words of (4) Highly prepared, (3) prepared, (2) less prepared and (1) unprepared.

For the third part which was the teaching qualities, LIKERT scaling was also used in the construction of the questionnaire with 1 to 4 scales such as (4) always practiced, (3) practiced, (2) less practiced and (1) not practiced at all; for classroom management, classroom instruction, professional development and collaborative activities.

The research instrument was subjected to pilot testing of 15 teachers who were non-respondents of the study and had undergone Cronbach Alpha analysis and reliability test. The final copy of the instrument was then administered to the actual respondents.

Table 2

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The table shows the results of the Cronbach analysis of the instrument for external validity and reliability. Cronbach's alpha is a method of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of common variance or covariance between the elements that make up a commodity and the amount of total variance. The idea is that if the tool is reliable, there should be a large covariance between items compared to the variance (LM Collins, 2007).

Based on the results, the questionnaire on school preparedness passed the validity and reliability testing since the item indicator per variable answers the target responses among the respondents and passed more than the 70%.

In terms of teaching quality, the item indicators passed the reliability and validity test also since it passed more than expected 70% passing rate of the Cronbach's Alpha. Cronbach's alpha is a convenient test used to estimate the reliability, or internal consistency, of a composite score (statisticssolutions.com,2022). Since the figures presented are more than .70, the instrument on teaching qualities passed the reliability and validity test viable for the conduct of the study.

Research Procedure

In the conduct of the study, the researcher prepared first the instrument to be used in the survey. It was submitted to the panel members for suggestions during the proposal.

After the proposal, suggestions were considered and revisions were made. The researcher then had the questionnaires that was validated by three external validators; one (1) School Head, one (1) Master Teacher, and one (1) Field expert. After all the comments and suggestions of the validators were incorporated in the survey questionnaires these were submitted to subject specialist for further checking.

Upon approval of the subject specialist, the researcher had an online consultation with the statistician and was given the signal to begin the pilot testing with (10) ten teachers who were not respondents of the study. The copies of the questionnaires for pilot testing were given to ten (10) respondents through google form link.

After the pilot testing, the results were tabulated in the data matrix template and was submitted to the statistician for Cronbach Alpha analysis for internal reliability and validity of the instruments.

To ensure the 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaire, the researcher herself personally distributed the hard copies of the questionnaires to the respondents of the eleven (11) schools of Candelaria West District. The researcher scheduled the distribution of the hard copies of the questionnaires and presented the approved letter of the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon Province and the District Supervisor to the (11) eleven school principals for the actual conduct of the study.

For ethical consideration, the researcher sought the permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon Province of Candelaria West District for the conduct of the study. The assistance of the (11) School Heads and Principals was also requested for a smooth and successful retrieval of the instrument.

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After all the prescribed requirements were accomplished and submitted, the data was submitted to the university's Stat Center for statistical treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3

Correlation between School Preparedness and Teaching Qualities in the Implementation of Face-To-Face Classes in the New Normal

School Preparedness	Teaching Qualities			
	Classroom Management	Classroom Instruction	Professional Development	Collaborative Activities
Physical Facilities	.598**	.487**	.320**	.430**
School Program	.463**	.362**	.223**	.389**
Safety Protocols	.574**	.459**	.272**	.419**
Students and Parents Awareness	.720**	.584**	.322**	.595**

Legend: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

This table presents the results of the correlation between school readiness and the quality of teaching of respondents when conducting face-to-face teaching in the new normal. Based on the figures above, all variables are correlated with each other, suggesting that school readiness, as perceived by respondents, has an important association with teachers' teaching qualities.

As can be seen, physical facilities and classroom management were significantly correlated with a p-value of 0.598 at the significance level of 0.01. This shows that a school's physical facilities have a significant impact on teachers' classroom management, including: B. The availability of materials and resources to facilitate student learning in a fun and engaging environment. When students stay in well-organized classrooms, positive learning that is informative and fun takes place.

As mentioned earlier, the physical environment and well-organized classrooms can have a bearing on both student performance and behavior. A well-maintained, safe, and quality physical environment promotes positive attitudes and motivations associated with student learning, academic performance, and prosocial behavior (safesupportivelearning.ed.gov, 2022).

A significant relationship is very clear for physical facilities and classroom education with a p-value of 0.487 at the significance level of 0.01. This demonstrates that teachers' preparation for face-to-face classes is a top priority when physical facilities are properly maintained and safe for students and teachers. The quality of school facilities is believed to influence teacher teaching and student learning when the physical facilities are complete, safe and well-functioning (sitelogiq.com (2022)).

For physical aptitude and professional development, a p-value of 0.320 was found to be correlated at the significance level of 0.01. Based on a teacher's cognitive level and instructional quality, physical facilities can affect a teacher's professional development. Attending conferences, trainings and even seminars in well-equipped schools motivates teachers to actively engage in the above activities. Despite the pandemic situation, teachers are willing to participate in such trainings and postgraduate programs as long as the school is safe, has adequate ventilation and comfortable seating and follows safety procedures as the pandemic is not over yet to do.

Therefore, the correlation between the two variables is very clear. A decent and safe facility is considered essential for a successful educational program (Planty, DeVoe, 2005).

There is an important link between them in terms of physical facilities and community activities. A p-value of 0.430 at a significance level of 0.01 indicates a significant relationship. Creating a positive and safe environment is necessary for teachers to effectively guide their students and keep them motivated and motivated to learn. In order to work well with other teachers and students, schools, especially public schools, need to be well equipped and not overcrowded to avoid the possibility of disease and viral transmission. This is very important for the health and welfare of teachers and students. important (safesupportivelearning.ed.gov, 2022).

These variables are highly correlated when it comes to school programs and the quality of education: classroom management, teaching, professional development, and community activities. The p-values for the above variables in the table are 0.463, 0.362, 223, and 0.389, respectively, suggesting that a well-prepared and planned school program creates a positive environment that fosters social interaction and creative learning. It is very clear that there are Effective teaching for students and effective teaching for

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teachers. It is hoped that the opening of schools to regular face-to-face classes will develop programs that will keep students, teachers and staff safe and secure.

Good communication between parents and students about policies and safety protocols improves the management of the classroom where learning takes place. Classroom instruction is considered to be within guidelines and following safety protocols if those involved are well-informed and ready for face-to-face instruction. Learning and collaborating with students and teachers is successful. The same is true for teacher professional development. Schools in safe environments encourage teachers to attend seminars, training sessions and workshops to update their skills in the new normal.

In addition, I am motivated to pursue postgraduate programs that are very helpful in achieving quality learning for my students. The design of good school programs in relation to face-to-face education is therefore of great importance in the midst of a pandemic, where everyone is informed and informed, so no one is protected against unforeseen events. cannot be held responsible (MCC, 2022).

These variables were found to correlate significantly with safety protocols and quality of education, including classroom management, classroom instruction, professional development, and collaborative activities. This can be inferred from p-values of 0.574, 0.459, 0.272, and 0.419, respectively, at the 0.01 significance level. This means that for better and more successful classroom management and instruction, appropriate adjustments to health and safety protocols in place around the world will make students, teachers and other stakeholder feel at ease. It shows that you need to get despite the low number of COVID-19 cases, these safety precautions are important because they also affect the interest of faculty who attend graduate programs or attend training courses or workshops when they are unsafe. Adherence to the precautions is still mandatory.

Likewise, collaboration is impossible if teachers and students were unaware of safety protocols. Therefore, this variable has a significant impact on the educational quality of respondents. Knowledge of safety protocols is a must for everyone given the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic, according to the Ministry of Education.

Concerning students' and parents' perceptions of 'dos' and 'don'ts', the quality of instruction has important associations with four variables. A P-value of 0.720 for classroom operations, 0.584 for classroom instruction, 0.322 for professional development, and a P-value for community activities of 0.595 were all significantly related to parent and student perceptions of safety procedures and policies in children's face-to-face classes. I'm here. learn. This suggests that when DepEd announced the start of in-person classes, schools provided students and parents with information about school emergency plans, parental access in an emergency, and school emergency contacts.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results presented, the following conclusions are drawn.

There is significant relationship between the preparedness of the schools in the face-to-face classes in terms of physical facilities, school programs, safety protocols, parents and student's awareness and teaching qualities such as classroom management, classroom instructions, professional development and collaborative activities. The school preparedness significantly affects the teaching quality of the teachers amidst face-to-face mode of teaching and learning. Thus, the hypothesis is *rejected*.

Established from the summary of findings and conclusions previously discussed and presented, the following recommendations are hereby suggested. School may continue designing a program that will continuously protect the student's health. Healthy and safety protocols may be followed with or without pandemic since the environment is not free from viruses and other bacteria that may harm the students and teachers as well so, observance of the policies and guidelines may be continued. Teachers may keep on improving their strategies and techniques to bring back the interest of the students to learn since they have been in hiatus for almost three years of face-to-face learning. Transition from distance learning to face-to-face learning will be easier if teachers will keep themselves updated on the new way of teaching using technology. In addition, mental health should also be the focused of teachers since pandemic brought negative mental and emotions to everyone. School and teachers may continue work collaboratively for the welfare of the students by keeping them aware of the necessary precautions to avoid untoward incidences. Parents may be given continuous orientation of the healthy home tips for the safety of their children. To ensure that teachers grow in their professional development, they must attend seminars, webinars, district trainings or even LAC sessions with the use of technology to strengthen their competencies in different areas of teaching and students learning.

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